

SYNTACTIC FEATURES OF ENGLISH PROVERBS ABOUT WEALTH AND POVERTY

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Abstract. This article is about specific features of proverbs about wealth and poverty, mainly about the structure of English proverbs. Proverbs about wealth and poverty often highlight the importance of financial stability and offer insights into the relationship between money and happiness. When examining the structure of English proverbs on these topics, several specific features can be observed.

Keywords: proverbs, sentence types, clauses, subclauses, compound, complex, compound-complex sentences, affirmative, negative form, communicative sentences

Proverbs appear in a variety of different sentence types; from a syntactic perspective, these sentences may be classified into four distinct types according to the number of clauses and sub-clauses they contain. These sentence types are: simple, compound, complex, and compound-complex. The most basic sentence is the simple sentence, which contains one main clause (subject and predicate) and no subclauses. They are typically simple, declarative, non-oppositional, and stylistically unmarked i.e. they do not contain many stylistic markers. [8;85]

They appear in both affirmative and negative form as can be seen in the examples below:

1. Affirmative (+)

Every man has his price.

Money opens all doors.

2. Negative (–)

Beggars cannot be choosers.

Wealth is nothing without health.[1]

Complex sentences contain one clause and one or more subclauses; the subclauses may be adjectival, nominal, or adverbial. The structural balance in these proverbs is asymmetrical, with the subclause being dependent on the main clause as can be seen in below, i.e. the subclause that will take no color cannot stand alone grammatically, and is tied to the main clause in which the subject bad cloth is contained. The subordinate clause often features a WH-subclause, which in English begins with one of the following: what, where, who, why, or when. [4;15] A stylistic feature of these proverbs is the repositioning of the subclause into sentence-initial position, usually for the purposes of emphasis as also can be seen in below:

He is rich that is satisfied. [Clause] + [Subclause]

He is rich enough who has true friends. [Clause] + [Subclause]

When poverty comes in the door love flies out at the window. [Subclause] + [Clause]

When riches increase, the body decreases. [Subclause] + [Clause] [3;371]

Compound sentences possess multiple independent clauses which are separated by a coordinator (in English these are for, and, nor, but, or, yet, so). There is a grammatical equality in these sentences, which balances the two clauses against one another through a central fulcrum in the shape of the coordinator. These examples often display a type of semantic equality or contrast, which is created through the replication of the syntactic pattern. In below we can see the two independent clauses falseness lasts an hour and truth lasts till the end of time located contiguously with the conjunction and acting as the central pivot.

Take care of the pence and the pounds will take care of themselves. [Clause] + [coordinator – and] + [Clause]

Often verbs are omitted from these proverbs and instead phrases are simply structurally juxtaposed with the implicit suggestion that there an underlying semantic relationship.

The compound–complex sentence is the most syntactically complicated type as it often features a multiplicity of clauses and subclauses. The minimum syntactic requirement is for at least two clauses and one subclause. The complex, extended structure is prohibitive to proverb composition, presumably because they are more difficult to memorize and recall in speech situations. [2;12]

Closely related to the aforementioned sentence types is the nominal sentence. This refers to a type of sentence with a predicate lacking a finite verb. Words and phrases are juxtaposed for the purposes of emphasis and intensity, but either there is no explicit grammatical connection between these phrases or the verbal construct has become redundant over time and is omitted. An oft-cited example of a nominal sentence is the proverb in this example in which the substantive verb to be is omitted:

Penny wise, pound foolish.

Much gold, much care. [7;116]

Sentences typically have four different functions: declarative (or indicative); interrogative; imperative; and exclamatory, which can be drawn together into two larger main groups: Affirmative and Communicative. Proverbs exhibit all these different functions, although some may be more frequently used than others. The first function is declarative (or indicative) which is a favored one in proverbs – as it is in natural speech – as it conveys information or ideas in the form of a statement. Interrogative sentences, on the other hand, take the form of a question. [5;30]

Affirmative:

- declarative/indicative:

A poor man is better than a liar.

Wit is better than wealth.

The communicative sentences types feature the imperative form in which an order is given. These, as we can imagine, were extremely common – although Mieder [6;137] has recently shown that this is no longer the case – as proverbs often give advice, counsel and instructions on how individuals should behave in both specific contexts and in general life.

In conclusion, understanding the structure and features of proverbs about wealth and poverty can provide insights into the cultural values and societal attitudes surrounding wealth and poverty in English-speaking cultures.

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